

Collaboration and Cowriting in Ancient Near Eastern Studies

A White Paper by the Centre of Excellence
in Ancient Near Eastern Empires

Ellie Bennett
Rick Bonnie
Joanna Töyräänvuori

Abstract

This white paper outlines the benefits and challenges of collaboration and cowriting within the context of ancient Near Eastern studies. While in recent years some large collaborative projects in ancient Near Eastern studies have been undertaken, the question remains why it is not practiced more. In the 'publish or perish' environment of modern Academia, producing publications quickly is in demand whereas in the humanities, ventures like collaborative writing are considered more time-consuming and, hence, are often sidelined.

We have found within the Centre of Excellence in Ancient Near Eastern Empires (ANEE) that collaboratively written publications are generally capable of producing more innovative research and may come with several benefits when compared to single-author papers. In the white paper we offer on behalf of the ANEE community our recommendations, discovered through trial and error, of how to make cowriting and collaborative enterprises more efficient and enjoyable for all parties involved.

Introduction

This white paper, written on behalf of the research community of the Centre of Excellence in Ancient Near Eastern Empires (ANEE), outlines the benefits and challenges of collaboration and cowriting within the context of ancient Near Eastern studies.¹ This is considered rather common practice outside of ancient Near Eastern studies, including in neighbouring fields like archaeology and digital humanities. While in recent years some large collaborative projects in ancient Near Eastern studies have been undertaken, the question remains why it is not practiced more. In the 'publish or perish' environment of modern academia,

producing publications quickly is in demand. In the humanities, ventures like collaborative writing are considered more time-consuming and, hence, are often sidelined.

The Centre of Excellence in Ancient Near Eastern Empires (2018-2025) at the University of Helsinki is a research community interested in how imperial identities changed in the first millennium BCE in the Middle East. It is split into three teams based on methods and approach: team 1 uses traditional archival research as well as digital methods; team 2 uses social science; and team 3 utilises archaeology. The

long timespan and diverse research methods means members of ANEE have necessarily had to collaborate with other members, particularly in publications. The experiences of members are that collaboratively written publications are generally capable of producing innovative research and come with a number of benefits when compared to single-author papers.

A key **benefit** of collaboration and cowriting is an increased complexity in research ideas which drives innovation. Diverse researchers bring a variety of ideas and perspectives to specific research problems. Researchers from differing backgrounds will increase access to

more expansive and/or better-quality data and methods.

Collaboration and cowriting allow for publications that garner more interest from other fields, which can lead to higher citations than single-author publications. This increases the impact of ancient Near Eastern research. Collaborative projects that produce such publications are generally looked at more favourably by funding bodies.

Collaboration and cowriting also leads to **challenges**: (1) interpersonal relationships; (2) timeline; and (3) interdisciplinary communication.

Under *interpersonal relationships*, the key challenges are, e.g., making compromises, which can challenge researchers who wish to push the envelope further than what the project allows for; requiring mutual trust; needing to choose colleagues that have complementary working styles and finding a mutually beneficial workflow with them, including juggling different university policies (e.g., software available to researchers); as well as maintaining a balance between disciplines and/or scholars, including how many authors participate and how they can meaningfully contribute.

Regarding the *timeline*, we have found that, e.g., scientific progress can be seen as slower

by individuals due to the need to compromise; setting of deadlines can be proven difficult and the time available differs by different participants; and short-term contracts in academia can impact the time available for sustained collaboration.

Interdisciplinary communication is made more difficult by different conventions, such as different writing styles, manners of data management, and finding publication venues that span the different disciplines. It may be difficult to get useful or constructive feedback before and in peer review. Differences in approaching how to solve ethical problems in research may also be an issue (e.g., plagiarism, data falsification,

unprovenanced objects), particularly when many authors are involved.

Finally, as an overarching challenge we found that it may be difficult to find a

research question that is equally interesting to all parties.

All of these challenges have been faced by ANEE at one time or another, as illustrated by the following case studies.

¹ Author names are given in alphabetical order, and all authors contributed equally. At the Centre of Excellence in Ancient Near Eastern Empires Annual Meeting in 2023, Scientific Advisory Board member Andrea Berlin suggested the lessons learned by the ANEE community in writing collaboratively be written down in a White Paper. Saana Svärd then organised a smaller, ANEE-wide discussion where all team

members could contribute their insight and experiences on the challenges, benefits, and other elements of collaborative writing in ancient Near Eastern studies. The authors of this paper then turned their comments into a rough first draft, which then was returned to the ANEE community for feedback that was incorporated into the White Paper. The White Paper was approved by the ANEE Board for publication.

Case Studies

Collaborative projects in ANEE – whether within or across the teams, as well as with external collaborators – have been encouraged from the very beginning. As such, our researchers have learned a lot about how to pursue collaboration and co-writing. The following case studies highlight how each of the three ANEE teams overcame some of the challenges and learned from the experiences. In addition to team-specific examples, we highlight an important cross-team collaboration.

Team 1: Computational Linguistics in Akkadian

Several members of Team 1 have been part of the ‘Semantic Domains in Akkadian Texts’ project (2016-2020, funded by the Academy of Finland), which aimed at testing and improving computational linguistic tools that

could be used on Akkadian corpora. The major hurdle was building a shared language between team members. Some were from a purely computational linguistics background, and others were trained as traditional Assyriologists. Whilst some members would understand terms like ‘word embeddings’ or ‘G-stem’, others would not be certain what

these meant. The members spent a great deal of time at the beginning of the project building a shared vocabulary and ensuring all members understood the state-of-the-art in their respective fields. Once these were established, the members were able to create meaningful research questions for both fields of study and test these computational linguistic tools in several publications.

Team 2: Historiography and Social Sciences

Team 2's work on ancient social biographies using Pierre Bourdieu's Field Theory resulted in not only co-learning in the form of team

retreats, workshops and co-reading of articles but also co-writing several articles with various combinations of team members. The project spanned across the lifetime of ANEE, allowing for different degrees of participation for members. This collaboration did not come about without a hitch, however, requiring the resolution of some interpersonal conflicts and with the withdrawal of a number of members from the project and from the core team. A key issue in the beginning stages of the project was finding a topic or approach that held connection to the work of all the members even marginally and that was not outside their sphere of interest. The difficulty in choosing a focus caused major challenges in

communication, resulting in various levels of effort put into the project and forced the team to compensate to strong discrepancy between engagement, finding ways to bring people into it without huge compromise. An issue of contention later on in the project was the order of authors in co-written publications which had not been agreed upon at the start of the project. As a compromise, different ordering of authors was used in different venues of publication.

Team 3: Community Heritage and Open Data Practices

In 'Discussing Ethical Practices in Archaeology: Decolonization, open data, and

community interaction', M. Lorenzon, R. Bonnie, and S. Thomas (2022) argue against the assumption that open data practices by archaeological projects increases the chance of looting of archaeological sites. Instead, they argue that a robust open data policy in connection with on the ground community engagement by archaeological projects develops mutual trust and, hence, forms a necessary step towards decolonization. While the topics brought together were rather novel, and developing the argument took some time, the project ran smoothly thanks to a strong mutual trust and flexibility in terms of working styles and compromises among the contributors. Building on a different set of expertise – decolonization

(Lorenzon), open data and illicit antiquities trafficking (Bonnie), and community archaeology (Thomas) – the project developed a novel argument that none of the individual contributors would and could have done independently.

Cross-team: Developing a Museum Exhibition

The museum exhibition ‘Exploring the Ancient Near East’ that ANEE developed took over five years and dozens of ANEE researchers across all teams, as well as collaborators across museums and other organisations. The exhibition was ultimately held at the National Museum of Finland,

Helsinki (May–Sept 2022) and at the Museum of Central Finland, Jyväskylä (Oct 2022–Jan 2023). The main challenges in conducting this highly collaborative project were finding a theme equally interesting for all parties, the making of compromises, scheduling across all involved, and personnel changes. The initial freedom allowed for the development of the theme and for the selection of the objects and displays which developed an exhibition fitting everyone’s interest. Yet, it equally led to various subsequent setbacks and practical issues, which meant that the exhibition changed drastically over time and many members had to accept compromises. With various organisations involved, each with different

characteristics, resources, and hopes for the exhibition, the scheduling and work on the exhibition was an obvious challenge.

Another challenge less often considered, however, was the various changes in the teams along the way. Some team members became less involved as the theme shifted away from their expertise, while newly hired museum personnel and ANEE researchers were later added. Researchers' temporary contracts and their key responsibilities to

publishing also meant that museum responsibilities were not always prioritised. That said, the benefits outweighed these challenges, as the developed exhibition became more complex and innovative than anyone foresaw, built primarily around objects from Finnish museums, with particular biographies connecting Finland's modern history to that of the ancient Near East.

Recommendations

Within all these case studies we have found common themes across the lifespan of the projects.

It is the recommendation of the authors (and the ANEE community) that researchers embarking on a collaborative project or are considering co-authoring a publication ought to **at the beginning** of the project:

- ✓ Agree on the **expected contributions and responsibilities** of each participant/member of the project. This includes writing and research, but also co-ordinating, leadership, data management responsibilities, and

authorship conventions for any future publications.

- ✓ Discuss and agree on the **workflow** of the project. Members of the project should be open to experimenting with different workflows and writing styles and practices. This includes the more mundane elements of research such as ensuring researchers have access to compatible writing and time/project management software, as well as communication platforms.
- ✓ Be clear on **time management**. Set aside plenty of time for the project, whilst also

being transparent about different participants' priorities and competing deadlines. Make sure deadlines are agreed upon and clear to all members. This is particularly important if the project will outlive any contracts of the participants, or there is a move to a new research environment.

- ✓ Ensure there is enough time built into the project to **establish and build trust** between members.
- ✓ Start recording and **documenting** the research process.
- ✓ Create a **data management plan** for the duration of the project.

- ✓ In publications, discuss and agree an **appropriate publication venue**, and the authorship conventions appropriate for that venue.
- ✓ Discuss the **motivations** of everyone on the project and be clear about what the project adds to all scholars' fields.
- ✓ Create a **common language** (e.g., communicating the state of the art in your field to outsiders) and agree on how to communicate (e.g., emails, online meetings, face to face).
- ✓ **Practice** explaining your point of view in a clear way with those unfamiliar with your research.

- ✓ Senior members are encouraged to take on a **mentoring** role within a project with more junior researchers.

During the project, it would be beneficial for the participants to

- ✓ Continue to **communicate** between participants; record and **document** the research process.
- ✓ Discuss the **progress**, aims, and goals of the project in case there is a need to pivot or change plans (or even terminate the project).

- ✓ Discuss whether the **project really adds to all scholars' fields**; set clear deadlines; create a shared understanding of the state-of-the-art in the field that is not your own.

- ✓ Be open to **trying different styles** of workflow and writing.
- ✓ Be open and prepared for **criticism**.
- ✓ Build **transparency and trust** between researchers about data and methods.

And finally, **at the end** of the project:

- ✓ Agree **how to communicate the results** to the public/scientific community.

✓ **Revise and update the plan** to share, maintain, or manage the outcomes of the project (e.g., datasets).

✓ **Reflect** on the collaboration and whether future collaborations can be facilitated or would be fruitful.

The ANEE community have found these recommendations through trial and error. It is our hope that other research communities within ancient Near Eastern studies take notice of them and are encouraged to embark on collaborative projects with these recommendations in mind.

Cover image: ANEE members in Jordan on their way to view a rock inscription. Photo by Jason Silverman.

Final image: ANEE members in a group exercise. Photo by Jason Silverman.

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